

On the Techno-Economic Viability of Coherent Point-to-Multipoint for Mobile Network Fronthaul

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Abstract: This work evaluates Point-to-Multipoint (P2MP) fronthaul for next-generation mobile networks, demonstrating cost and energy savings compared to traditional Point-to-Point (P2P) and Wavelength Division Multiplexing (WDM) architectures across diverse deployment scenarios. © 2025 The Author(s)

1. Introduction

With the evolution towards 6G, the fronthaul segment is expected to become even more bandwidth demanding. As such, coherent technologies represent the only feasible solution to deliver the required levels of bandwidth. However, adopting traditional Point-to-Point (P2P) and Wavelength Division Multiplexing (WDM) approaches can prove costly and complex when scaling to meet the increasing demands of 6G networks.

The goal of Point-to-Multipoint (P2MP) is to provide an efficient solution for network segments where traffic aggregation is essential, in contrast to the traditional approach of mapping the networks solely through P2P networking [1]. Due to its inherent nature, P2MP is well-suited for the fronthaul segment, where multiple Radio Units (RUs) need to be connected to a site hosting the centralized Distributed Unit (DU). In fact, by leveraging Digital Subcarrier Multiplexing (DSCM), P2MP can dynamically allocate bandwidth across multiple nodes, providing improved scalability and resource utilization while reducing the number of required transceivers and fiber links [2]. Recent advancements in coherent technologies and DSCM have enabled the development of P2MP transceivers and node solutions capable of supporting high-capacity, cost-effective fronthaul solutions [3,4]. These transceivers utilize DSCM to subdivide the wavelength spectrum into multiple digital subcarriers, each independently managed and allocated, which allows for flexible bandwidth distribution and efficient traffic aggregation. This capability makes P2MP an attractive option for next-generation mobile transport networks, especially in urban and suburban environments where traffic demands are highly variable.

However, as P2MP is still an emerging technology, there is a need to evaluate its techno-economic applicability for fronthaul deployment in next-generation mobile networks where the cost of transport can compromise economic sustainability. This paper aims to assess the feasibility and benefits of adopting P2MP in comparison with traditional P2P and WDM approaches across various deployment scenarios, including dense urban, urban, suburban, and rural environments. We show that while the migration towards P2MP requires limited effort in terms of Capital Expenditure (CAPEX), it introduces significant reductions in energy consumption, demonstrating that P2MP can provide a cost-effective alternative to current fronthaul architectures with the possibility to maintain a high level of performance.

Fig. 1. Reference Architectural Solutions

Fig. 2. CAPEX and Annual Energy Consumption Comparison

2. System Model

Fig. 1 shows the reference architectural solutions considered in this work. The network architecture used for this evaluation consists of four different configurations: Point-to-Point (P2P), Wavelength Division Multiplexing (WDM), Point-to-Multipoint (P2MP), and Point-to-Multipoint with Pre-Aggregation (P2MP-WP). Each configuration is applied to four distinct geotypes as defined in [5]: dense urban, urban, suburban, and rural. Here, we consider the transport solutions for realizing the fronthaul of the mobile network, i.e., interconnecting RUs with heterogeneous capacity to DUs, either physical or virtual (vDUs), located at a Central Office (CO) site.

In the P2P configuration, RUs are connected to a Cell Site Router/Switch (CSR) via Short Reach grey transceivers. The traffic is aggregated by the CSR and sent to the CO using a dedicated fiber link and Long Reach Grey transceivers. The traffic is then disaggregated at the CO by a Central Office Router/Switch (COR) equipped with high-capacity Grey transceivers. This architecture provides high reliability and capacity but may result in high Operational Expense (OPEX) due to the need for power-consuming packet switches.

The WDM architecture introduces wavelength multiplexing to aggregate multiple RUs on a shared fiber using different wavelengths. 10G-400G grey and WDM transceivers are used in combination with transponders and multiplexing equipment to achieve wavelength multiplexing, allowing multiple signals to be transmitted simultaneously over the same fiber. Although this architecture enables efficient fiber usage, it requires complex and costly hardware, which could significantly impact CAPEX. By employing DSCM, the P2MP architecture leverages a shared optical link to connect multiple RUs to the CO. Each cell site is equipped with a demarcation unit hosting grey transceivers with a minimum granularity of 25G, which are conveyed onto digital subcarriers via P2MP Leaf pluggable modules and aggregated at P2MP Hub modules with up to $16 \times 25G$ capacity at the CO. This assumption is in line with a current DSCM transceiver implementation [1]. While enabling fiber link sharing, this approach, thanks to its ability to aggregate multiple subcarriers, reduces the need for switches at the cell site, making it a promising cost-effective solution. Since the P2MP has a minimum granularity of 25G, fronthaul segments requiring low bandwidth may lead to inefficient utilization of DSCM. The P2MP-WP configuration extends the P2MP architecture by incorporating a packet pre-aggregation level via a low-capacity CSR responsible for packing multiple low-capacity fronthaul segments onto a single DSCM channel. The P2MP-WP solution enhances the resource efficiency of P2MP at the cost of introducing an additional switching level.

3. Results

We considered four different deployment scenarios to evaluate the proposed fronthaul solutions: dense urban, urban, suburban, and rural environments. The area sizes for these scenarios range from 0.64 to 163.84 square kilometers. The different geotypes correspond to unique topologies and compositions of macro and small cell sites, each with distinct radio deployments involving multiple radio bands and bandwidths, reflecting Medium Term (MT) and Long Term (LT) capacity requirements. Total cell site fronthaul required capacity spans from 43.2 Gbps for small cells in the MT to 324 Gbps for macro cells in the LT. For the CAPEX calculation and comparison and for each scenario examined, we include the cost of all components required for implementing the network infrastructure between the RUs and DUs. For this purpose, we define a cost model based on publicly available prices for widely adopted and mature devices, such as IMDD transceivers (grey or WDM) with different reaches (Short Reach (SR) 100m; Extended Reach (ER) 30km), WDM mux/demux units, and routers of various sizes. The model uses the cost of a commercial P2P 400G ER transceiver as its reference cost unit (CU). For devices that are still in R&D or pre-commercial phases (e.g., coherent DSCM P2MP hub and leaf modules), we assume a 35% cost increase over an equivalent-capacity grey transceiver, reflecting the surcharge for additional advanced

features. While we recognize the inherent limitations of this approach, it provides a useful and meaningful basis for comparison. As shown in Fig. 2(a-d), we distinguish between switching and transmission equipment costs. Since TCO is significantly impacted by OPEX, and energy represents the main OPEX contributor among the different architectural solutions, we also analyze the annual energy consumption of the deployed equipment. Results show that WDM is the most expensive solution due to the complexity of the transmission equipment required, leading to a CAPEX increase of up to 125% compared to P2P across all scenarios. P2MP generally demonstrates viable CAPEX performance, offering a lower overall expenditure compared to WDM and a competitive position relative to P2P, particularly when considering P2MP's potential to reduce OPEX. Specifically, in the urban scenario, where the combination of fronthaul flows allows for a reduction in the number of transmission devices used, P2MP-WP can even achieve a CAPEX reduction of up to 10% in the medium and long term.

In terms of energy consumption, the annual consumption for P2MP and P2MP-WP architectures is significantly lower compared to P2P and WDM. For instance, in dense urban areas, P2MP solutions consume up to 70% less energy compared to P2P solutions, highlighting the efficiency of P2MP in managing both MT and LT power requirements. Similar trends are observed in suburban and rural scenarios, where the P2MP and P2MP-WP configurations demonstrate better energy efficiency, making them more sustainable for long-term deployment. Fig. 2(e-h) shows the annual energy consumption (E) for the transmission and switching components. In terms of energy, the annual consumption for P2MP and P2MP-WP architectures is significantly lower compared to P2P and WDM due to the substantial reduction of switching devices. It is worth mentioning that P2MP-WP offers higher efficiency in terms of resource utilization at the cost of increased hardware complexity and energy consumption. For example in dense urban areas, P2MP solutions consume up to 70% less energy compared to P2P solutions, highlighting the efficiency of P2MP in managing both MT and LT power requirements. Similar trends are observed in suburban and rural scenarios, where the P2MP and P2MP-WP configurations demonstrate better energy efficiency, making them more sustainable for long-term deployment.

4. Conclusion

In this work, we evaluated the techno-economic performance of coherent P2MP as a fronthaul solution for next-generation mobile networks. It is worth noting that, while energy estimation parameters are less subject to uncertainty, CAPEX evaluation is more affected by market dynamics. However, this does not alter the overall validity of P2MP's ability to offer significant potential for OPEX reduction while requiring only a reduced CAPEX difference compared to traditional approaches. The results demonstrate that P2MP solutions offer a cost-effective and energy-efficient alternative to traditional P2P and WDM architectures, making them a promising choice for diverse deployment scenarios.

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